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Introduction

Negative impacts of invasive alien plants (IAPs) on biodiversity and ecosystem goods and services are frequently demonstrated in the literature. Land-users' income and livelihoods, especially that of marginalized communities, are believed to be particularly vulnerable. However, IAPs also provide benefits for people (e.g. fodder, medicinal uses, etc.). Working for Water (WfW) was established to manage IAPs with the aim of empowerment through job creation; it requires the support of private landholders to manage invasive species and therefore an understanding of how IAPs influence livelihoods is pertinent to the success of such a programme. Research in this regard is scarce, especially in South Africa.

Key questions include:

- i. What are people's attitudes towards and perceptions of IAPs?
- ii. How important are IAPs for human well-being and livelihoods?
- iii. What are the impacts of IAP management and eradication programmes on livelihoods?

Research design and Methodology

- Elim on the Agulhas Plain (AP) was selected as study site (see **Figure 1**). Elim land is owned by the Moravian Church.
- Interviewees were identified following a snowball sampling approach.
- Data were collected through basic qualitative, individual interviews.
- A total of 24 interviews were conducted:
 - Farmers; N = 12
 - Rural community; N = 12
- Transcribed interviews were coded with MAXQDA 10, a Qualitative Data Analysis package, and analysed with MS Excel.
- Used method from Botha et al. (2008) to report results.
- Themes grouped into 7 main topics under the benefits and costs associated with IAPs (See **Table 1**).

References

- Botha, S., P. J. Carrick, and N. Allsopp. 2008. Capturing lessons from land-users to aid the development of ecological restoration guidelines for lowland Namaqualand. *Biological Conservation*. 14:885-895.
- Magadla, D., and N. Mdzeke. 2004. Social benefits in the Working for Water programme as a public works initiative. *South African Journal of Science*. 100:94-96.
- Van Wilgen, B. W., D. C. Le Maitre, and R. M. Cowling. 1998. Ecosystem services, efficiency, sustainability and equity: South Africa's Working for Water programme. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*. 13:378-378.

Legend:

Figure 1. Map of the Agulhas Plain, indicating the extent of the Moravian Church ground (hatching). Interviews with farmers were conducted to the north of Elim. Exact location of interview sites is not given to ensure anonymity of interviewees.

Photo 1

Photo 2

Photo 4

Photo 3

Photo 1. Job creation through WfW as a means of poverty alleviation.

Photo 2. IAPs create fire risks that are detrimental to people's livelihoods.

Photo 3. Secondary industries as a means of sustainable alien clearing was highlighted through the interviews.

Photo 4. Spiny foliage of *Hakea* spp. impede flower picking as well as alien clearing.

Benefits	Costs
Direct use ^{6,24}	Costs associated with direct use ^{1,14}
Economic use ^{8,10}	Costs associated with economic use ^{4,17}
Indirect benefit ^{8,17}	Indirect costs ^{7,32}
	Management costs ^{53,17}

Table 1. Perceived costs and benefits of IAPs. Codes were grouped into 3 benefit and 4 cost categories. Superscripts indicate the number of times farmers and community members respectively referred to these categories.

Key findings

- Land under more intense management had fewer IAPs and contributed to less antagonistic attitudes towards IAPs. Attitudes were also positively influenced by the level of benefit derived through IAPs.
- Firewood from IAPs is used more extensively in economically deprived households as opposed to affluent households.
- Despite Elim being fully electrified, IAPs still play a pivotal role as an energy source in this economically marginalized community.
- Certain IAPs (e.g. *Leptospermum laevigatum*, *Acacia cyclops*, *Acacia mearnsii*) are highly favoured as firewood due to inherent qualities i.e. high combustion temperature and long-lasting coals.
- Very few farmers expressed considerable positive valuation for IAPs. Those that did value it as fodder, potential to make mulch, fence poles and furniture from it.
- IAP clearing success was perceived to be variable; farmers emphasised that it is a protracted process that demands excessive financial resources.
- In addition to benefitting the community through the conventional social development goals set out by WfW, other benefits were derived (i.e. pride, community unity, conflict management skills, feelings of responsibility and enhanced work ethic).

Future implications

- Invasive alien plant eradication programmes should continue but should take into account the benefits and uses of these plants by local people.
- Local land-users and the community at large must be educated regarding IAPs to prevent seeds and propagules from spreading when plants are being moved (as fuelwood, etc.)
- Government should invest more in secondary wood industries in order to generate revenues for a more sustainable alien clearing initiative.
- Land-users must be informed regarding effective clearing methods to minimize costs in terms of time and money.
- Social development should be integrated more fully in WfW's goals.